

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS EnvironmentS
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP2

D2.1 LAA Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines

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Executive summary

These guidelines support the design and implementation of a sustained stakeholder engagement strategy for LENSES, with a strong focus on pilot-level Learning and Action Alliances (LAA).

As a first step, the document introduces the importance of a carefully planned participatory activities for the successful implementation of Nexus approaches and provides a conceptual basis for stakeholder engagement activities in LENSES (sections 1 and 2).

Preliminary versions of this deliverable were shared with the pilots to provide guidance on how to conduct stakeholder mapping processes and set-up the regional LAAs. This information is also included in this final version (section 3).

The final step is supporting the pilots in the selection of the LENSES methods that better fit to their challenges and needs. These methods are mapped within section 4, describing each method and informing on objectives, activities, requirements for implementation and expected outcomes. Section 5 deepens on the importance of designing a comprehensive engagement strategy throughout all the project and provides guidance on how to design a sustained engagement strategy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. What are these stakeholder engagement guidelines?

These guidelines are supporting the stakeholder engagement activities conducted within the LENSES pilots, mainly as part of the planned activities in the Pilot Learning and Action Alliances (LAA).

The guidelines intend to provide both a conceptual basis (e.g. why participatory approaches are a core activity in the LENSES strategy) and guidance for the practical implementation of these approaches. Following this aim, the document is divided into two separate parts, aiming to:

- a) Describe the **conceptual basis** for stakeholder engagement and participation in LENSES. The stakeholder engagement process seeks to create active communities of actors who share knowledge and experiences in order to build common visions toward improved and resilient Nexus systems. This conceptual basis will facilitate the pilot leaders to communicate why LENSES participatory approaches will support social learning and provide robust support to planning and decision-making.
- b) Support the **development of participatory approaches** by:
 - Supporting the process of stakeholder mapping.
 - Helping to coordinate the participatory approaches with the specific work-plan defined for each pilot for the implementation of LENSES methods and approaches at different levels.
 - Providing guidance on setting-up the pilot LAAs.
 - Identifying activities and methods to promote the active participation of stakeholders in LENSES.

These guidelines are conceived as a living working document, to be initially circulated by the first project plenary meeting and then regularly updated as the project evolves until its final submission by month 12 of the project, i.e. April 2022.

1.2. Some key concepts

“ A **stakeholder** is any person or group who influences, or is influenced by, the project. In practice, this implies actors that are affected by a problem at stake and/or have the capacity to change the course of action in a given territory. ”

“ **Engagement** is defined as the active involvement and participation of others in one or more parts of the project. ”

“ **Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)** are cooperative, horizontal forums where stakeholders can bring their expertise, but talk freely outside of any organisational constraints in an atmosphere of mutual trust and ownership. ”

“ LENSES acknowledges the importance of **different types of knowledge**, e.g. academic knowledge, practical knowledge, theoretical knowledge, and the LAA are the social structures devoted to facilitate and catalyse the integration of these. ”

“ **Social learning** is a core objective of the LAA social structure. Social learning emphasizes the importance of observing, understanding and imitating the behaviours and attitudes of other stakeholders. ”

2. CONCEPTUAL BASIS

Participatory approaches are increasingly demanded and implemented for tackling complex challenges (i.e. Nexus-related challenges), since these often require multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary solutions. This is mainly because stakeholder engagement has the capacity to reduce conflict, build trust and facilitate learning amongst stakeholders and publics, who are then more likely to support project goals and implement decisions in the long term. In other words, more often the course of action will only change if actors are being listened to and their priorities and perceptions understood.

The sectors and actors in the WEF Nexus (Water-Ecosystems-Food Nexus) often have different priorities and limited knowledge exchange and communication.

2.1. Why stakeholder engagement is important to LENSES

The focus of LENSES is on WEF+C (Water-Ecosystems-Food + Climate) Nexus, and it is fundamental to acknowledge that the identification of challenges and needs, as well as the identification and adoption of potential solutions require an ambitious stakeholder engagement strategy.

A key challenge is to address the so-called “science-policy gap” and generate several benefits and opportunities, among others:

1. The **integration of different types of knowledge** from multiple sources and perspectives improves the ability to understand and manage complex, rapidly changing social-ecological systems. These exchanges facilitate negotiation and mutual learning among stakeholders, reduce conflict and increase support and actor buy-in for decisions made.
2. The inclusion of stakeholder engagement processes enhances the **quality of the research** by considering more comprehensive information inputs and the impact of the research by helping to frame questions that are not just scientifically but also socially relevant.
3. Participatory processes have shown to have significant improvements in lifting institutional and technical **capacities for Nexus management**.
4. These participatory approaches also contribute to raising **awareness**, increasing the **social impact** of project results, or fostering the establishment of collaborative communities in the territory, among many others.

2.2. Why stakeholder engagement is not always effective

Despite the benefits of enhancing and incorporating stakeholder participation, there are also some explanatory factors for the success or failure of participatory processes that need to be taken into consideration (Reed et al, 2010; Choi et al, 2005):

- **Scientists and decision-makers** often have different goals (e.g. advancing science versus obtaining popular support), they search for different things (e.g. the truth using a rational model versus a compromise, using an intuitive model), they speak different languages (e.g. scientific language requires translation to be understood by non-scientists, versus decision-makers who speak their own language full of acronyms), and importantly, the timescale (i.e. research can take very long and end up suggesting more research is needed, versus decision-makers who require instant answers).
- **Socio-economic, cultural, and institutional contexts** affect the success of an engagement process, e.g. existence of participatory culture and former experiences of engagement (whether successful or unsuccessful) and available resources. For these reasons, it is necessary to take time to fully understand the local context in which engagement is to be enacted, to determine what type of engagement approach is appropriate, and enable the design of any process to be effectively adapted to the context.
- The **design of the process** needs to take into consideration a proper representation of the relevant public and stakeholder interests; adequate transparency with stakeholders; and the inclusion of multiple knowledge sources. Power dynamics is one of the significant reasons for engagement failing to deliver outcomes, so this is an aspect that needs to be well considered in the design of the participatory activities, i.e. assuring that everyone is given an equal opportunity to contribute.
- **Expectations from stakeholders** must be well clarified and complied, i.e. results enriched through the participatory process must be translated into meaningful information, knowledge, or lifted capacities. Regarding this, engagement processes in LENSES are not understood as stakeholder being data providers. While stakeholders in some cases might be also experts and have access to relevant data, stakeholders are not necessarily experts, nor their interest in engaging in a participatory process is only to provide, but also obtain in exchange. Another problem we want to avoid is understanding engagement as a one-way communication ,e.g. scientists presenting their ideas and findings instead of having a two-way communication.

2.3. How stakeholder engagement is understood by LENSES

From the above, it is crucial for LENSES to have a good understanding of:

- i) what is / what is not a stakeholder and a participatory process; and
- ii) clearly define and manage the expectations and efforts required from all the participants.

To bear in mind before starting any engagement activity:

- **Data providers and Stakeholders are DIFFERENT actors.** An expert and data provider could also be a stakeholder, but a stakeholder is not necessarily a data provider and should not be treated as such.
- **INFORMING** stakeholders about research outcomes, goals, and tools is **NOT equivalent to ENGAGING**. The motivation to engage must stem from the scientist's desire to answer meaningful questions for stakeholders or support the development of a knowledge base that can increase the social impact of the project in addition to any scientific goal.
- The success of the overall strategy will primarily rely upon the definition of a **good engagement strategy for each pilot**: **WHY** we want to engage, for **WHAT** purpose, **WHOM** we need to engage, and **HOW much** will be required from stakeholders and **WHAT** will they get in return.

3. LENSES PARTICIPATORY PROCESSES: INITIAL ENGAGEMENT

To carry out a successful participatory process, it will be essential to design the overall approach by following a series of steps carefully:

- 1) Identifying key stakeholders to be involved (see section 3.1 on stakeholder mapping);
- 2) Introducing the project and the pilot challenges and fundamental objectives to the relevant stakeholders in the different Nexus domains (see section 3.2);
- 3) Ensuring compliance with ethical requirements on data protection and human involvement in research (see section 3.3);
- 4) Defining the purpose and expected outcomes of the participatory processes to manage stakeholder expectations (see section 3.4 on the organization of workshops);
- 5) Identifying the most suitable methods and means of implementing the proposed activities (see section 4 for a brief description of LENSES methods to be applied in a participatory way); and
- 6) elaborating a detailed plan of participatory activities (see section 5).

3.1. Stakeholder mapping

In this section, we aim to provide pilot leaders with a systematic (yet flexible) methodology to map key stakeholders in each pilot through a series of steps:

STEP 1: Draft the initial list of stakeholders

Each pilot team should develop a preliminary list of potential stakeholder groups. For instance, by listing all relevant organizations that project partners know and that are connected to the problems at stake. Similarly, project partners can informally approach their contacts and apply the so-called snowball technique, i.e. ask already identified stakeholders who else should be approached and invited. Last but not least, a

complementary approach is to investigate the existence of already established stakeholder networks (e.g. from previous projects or community of practices within the region, etc.).

One recommendation is to use “snowballing techniques” by asking some identified stakeholders about what people and institutions they consider should be engaged in the participatory processes, thus increasing stakeholders list.

STEP 2: Ensure diversity and well-balanced representation of all types of actors and sectors

Make sure you have all relevant sectors represented and correct any important bias. In this regard, pilot partners need to ensure a balanced representation of:

- Different sectors (i.e. water, food, environment).
- The number of actors belonging to different sectors.
- The type of actors (e.g. policy-makers, public and private decision-makers, citizen organizations, academia, etc).
- All institutional and governance levels that are relevant to the issues at stake (e.g. national, regional, local).
- Coherence with the LENSES Gender Action Plan (see D8.1).

STEP 3: Suitability assessment of identified stakeholders

Once the long list has been created, it is recommended to map actors against two criteria: influence and importance. Influence is defined here as the capacity/power of an actor to solve or exacerbate the problem. Interest relates to how the problem matters to the actor (i.e. It is in their interest to solve it? Is this problem a major issue for their business?). Some practical tips for this exercise:

- To the long list of stakeholders representing the different sectors and types of actors, add a short and brief description of how each actor is connected to the nexus problem at stake (e.g. causing the problem, advocating for a solution, impacted by the problem caused by third parties, with capacity to manage/solve the problem, etc).
- Assess the influence and interest of each stakeholder (-, 0, +) qualitatively.
- Create a plot like the one below (see Figure 2) and place the stakeholders in the different quadrants.

Figure 1. Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria.

Usually, the stakeholders with a high level of interest and influence are the ones we are most interested to collaborate with. Other stakeholders with either a high level of interest or influence will also be engaged in the participatory activities, with a main role at the level of involvement and consultation. A key group is those stakeholders with a high level of influence and low interest. This group may have a significant influence on the success of the approach. However, they may be challenging to engage, so most of our engagement efforts should be devoted to attracting them to our participatory activities. Stakeholders with low interest and influence will be informed and communicated about the project but not often be included in the participatory process.

There is not an optimum number of stakeholders to be involved and a balance must be maintained in terms of sectoral representation to avoid sectors having an excessive predominance over others.

Depending on the level of commitment and availability, pilot teams could decide as well to have a core and extended group of stakeholders. Core members are those with a high interest in the problems at stake and probably also enough time availability to engage in numerous activities, whereas the extended group can embrace the full list.

In the LENSES Nexus contexts, using a gender perspective and enabling the integration of women's knowledge of the environment will increase the chances of environmental sustainability.

Results from this stakeholder mapping exercise for most of the LENSES pilots are included in Annex 1.

3.2. Introducing LENSES to the main stakeholders

With the aim of supporting the pilot teams in the first stages of the stakeholder engagement, WP2 produced a set of dedicated materials:

- **Guidelines to support the organisation of the initial LAA meeting** in each pilot (included in Annex 2 of this deliverable). This LAA kick-off meeting coincides with the first (out of five) regional meetings to be organised in each pilot throughout the project. The guidelines contain several sections that can be distributed in advance as standalone briefs or as an introductory package to the participants in the meeting: i) A general introduction to LENSES project; ii) A general introduction to the Local Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) (i.e. challenges, aims, proposed structure); and iii) Description of the recommended activities to be included in the LAA Kick-Off meeting.
- **The LENSES welcome presentation to stakeholders** as a support material to establish initial contact with local stakeholders, e.g. an initial email with the invitation to participate in the workshop or any other participatory activity. A full version of this welcome presentation (in English) was forwarded to all pilot leaders (see Annex 3), with the recommendation to enrich the presentation with more specific information for each pilot (e.g. key challenges and objectives) and translate the material into the local language.
- **A LENSES 1-pager** (see Annex 4) also as a support material to facilitate initial contacts with local stakeholders (after translation into the local language).

3.3. Informed consent form

In order to comply with the ethical research requirements imposed by our Contracting Authority (the Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area: ‘the PRIMA Foundation’), each LENSES pilot team needs to ensure that each stakeholder involved in any participatory activity signs in advance an informed consent form. The informed consent form in Spanish and English (see Annex 5) has been shared with the pilot teams and is also available in the project shared folder.

It is the responsibility of each pilot team to translate this form into the local language and to use it in all participatory meetings (e.g. workshops), interviews, and participatory activities with local stakeholders. This informed consent form contains relevant information for stakeholders to clearly understand: a) What the project LENSES is about (e.g., an introduction to the LENSES project describing its objectives and main methodologies); b) What is the participatory action, and what their participation will consist of; c) How the data collected will be processed, stored and disseminated (e.g., if their input will be anonymized); and d) how to revoke the informed consent at any time.

Each Pilot leader must ensure that all stakeholders involved in LENSES participatory activities receive, understand, and sign this informed consent prior to the development of the activity.

3.4. Recommendations for the organisation of a successful workshop

Workshops will be the core participatory activities in LENSES, involving a broader group of stakeholders for interaction, exchange and co-development. The organisation and development of a workshop require many resources and opportunities to engage with the broad group of stakeholders are limited. Therefore, it is vital to plan ahead and carefully prepare the organisation of these workshops. This section provides several recommendations for the organisation of successful and impactful workshops.

As a first point, the organisation and conduction of these participatory processes with stakeholders should follow a series of key principles.

1. Objectives should be clearly stated;
2. Methods should be adapted to the local cultural/institutional/context;
3. There should be a broad range of interested parties/individuals;
4. Transparency in using the information: it is key to make clear how stakeholders’ views will be used and what the information resulting from the workshop will serve for;
5. Allocate sufficient time to carry out the activities without overloading the participants. Some time for breaks and networking is necessary and helps create connection and engagement between the participants;
6. Stakeholders should receive intermediate feedback and a summary of results and conclusions from their contributions during the course of the process;
7. The results of the process should have an impact on the decision to be made or the process in which they are to be involved;
8. We should search for evidence of enhanced stakeholder understanding – i.e. social learning.

Having these keys in mind, structuring the organisation of stakeholder engagement participatory processes can be done in a series of sequential steps. These steps describe the methodological backbone and logic to develop a coherent and fruitful participatory workshop or session, as well as the elements and aspects to be prepared and taken into account. However, on a broader sense, the methodological logic can also be applied to structure the whole participatory process composed of several iterative workshops, where stakeholders embark on several phases of the process with bilateral information exchanges: stakeholders provide information and insights and receive feedback and results from previous phases.

Steps for the organization of a participatory workshop:

STEP 1. Define the objectives. You should define the primary and secondary objectives of the workshop. The following questions can help identify both categories' objectives.

- *What do we need to get (outcomes) from the participation process: information (quantitative, qualitative, perceptions, awareness...)?*
- *In which format do we need the information: numbers, causal relations, concrete data, general knowledge, perceptions, spatial representations...?*
- *Are we seeking any additional effects besides our main inputs: e.g. building sense of community, raising awareness, promoting networking and communication between the actors, foster/show transparency, educate on something/disseminate information...?*

STEP 2. Define the best methodology to obtain the required outcomes. Depending on the type of outcome and the format required, a different methodology or set of methodologies will be more convenient. A set of examples of methodologies suited for obtaining different outcomes is provided in Annex 6. Once the methodology has been selected, the most logical and efficient sequence of steps should be defined, optimising time and resources while ensuring the achievement of results.

STEP 3. Materials and resources needed: once the exercises and dynamics have been designed, a list of required materials and resources should be prepared to ensure everything needed can be available. If some critical element cannot be accessed, an alternative should be searched for (alternative material, adapted exercise or an alternative method). Examples of valuable materials are PPTs, postcards, board charts, blackboards, stickers, etc.

STEP 4. Define the agenda and prepare a dissemination and an internal working agenda: Once the agenda has been closed, it is useful to prepare two versions:

- Dissemination agenda: should include the title, logistics and main schedule of the workshop activities. It is aimed for sharing with the participants to provide them with the essential information and attract their interest.
- Internal working agenda: it should contain the same items as the external agenda, completed with the distribution of tasks among the organising team and the preparation details, as a sort of a script for the organisation and conduction of the workshop. Possible tasks include overall moderation, facilitation of groups, note-taking, generation of visual material (pictures, videos), etc.

STEP 5. Pilot workshop

Carry out a pilot test of the workshop to make sure the exercises can be done within the allocated time, to foresee any possible unexpected situations (questions, polemics), prepare responses, and make the organising team get hold of their tasks. Make any adjustments as required.

STEP 6. Define the list of actors to be invited

Ensure that all the interested groups are represented, and there is a certain balance, unless the workshop's objective is especially focused on one or two specific groups.

STEP 7. Logistics

- Prepare logistics: book a place for the venue, book the catering/drinks, prepare and buy the materials with time.
- Send the invitations to the participants via email and make any personal contacts (by phone or in-person) for those stakeholders potentially more difficult to reach via email (i.e. farmers, elder people, etc.).
- Ask for confirmation of assistance and send reminders when the event gets closer. Some additional phone calls may help get further responses if the response rate has been low.
- Prepare attendance list and informed consent forms (see Annex 1) for the use of images, data protection, possible sharing of email among participants, and attendance forms.
- Organize and manage reimbursement of travel costs if applicable.
- Prepare accreditation tags.

STEP 8. Process evaluation

Undertaking some kind of process evaluation is important in order to assess: 1) the quality of the process, 2) the satisfaction of participants / Suggestions for improvement, 3) to gather additional individual-based information or feedback, 4) assess the perception of usefulness, learning from the process. This can be done through forms or surveys at the end of the day, or an evaluation email submitted one or two days after the workshop. Generally, the onsite feedback gathering method will gather more responses than ex-post via email.

STEP 9. Post-workshop processing tasks

- Send a thanking email to the attendees.
- Gather and digitalize the information co-produced with stakeholders during the workshop.
- Analyse the information and turn it into usable results for the project/process' aims. Draw out a few conclusions from the session.
- Prepare a summary note of the workshop, including the results and conclusions achieved, and disseminate it among participants.
- Proceed to the reimbursement of travel expenses if applicable.

Final specific keys or recommendations to ensure the success of a participatory workshop or session include the following:

- Make sure to explain very well the objective of the workshop and how it fits within the broader project/process, and if there will be future follow up/next phase sessions.
- Explain how the inputs from the participants will be included.
- Explain carefully what the role of the participants is and what they will be asked to do during the session.
- Send a summary of results and conclusions 2 or 3 weeks after the workshop and another final summary by the end of the process/project.
- Provide information that may be useful/interesting for the participants.

- Ensure a good moderation so all the participants feel equally encouraged to contribute and there is an atmosphere of respect, order, and equality.
- Try to integrate the stakeholders' interests in the discussion topics/exercises to ensure a balance between their concerns and needs and the specific objectives of the process.
- Make always sure that stakeholders end up with a feeling that their opinions have been listened to and taken into account.

A catalogue of methodologies and event formats for the dynamisation of workshops is added as Annex 6.

4. METHODOLOGIES FOR CO-CREATING A NEXUS SYSTEMIC APPROACH

LENSES develops and applies several methodologies and tools through a participatory approach. This section provides a brief description of each method focusing on the participatory actions to be conducted. This information steers the design of the participatory activities in each pilot. The full list of methodologies with a participatory component is compounded by:

- Visioning (WP2)
- Participatory System Dynamics Model (PSDM) for scenario analysis (WP3)
- Mapping policy context and developing policy scenarios (WP4)
- Nature-based Solutions (NbS) selection framework (WP5)
- Nature-based Solutions business cases (WP6)
- Climate Risk Assessment (WP7)
- Land use mapping & land use suitability (WP7)
- Water accounting, allocation, and planning (WP7)
- Linking Nexus management to SDG delivery (WP7)
- Storytelling (WP9)

The application of this catalogue of methodologies to the LENSES pilots will consider that:

- a) Not all methodologies will be applied to all pilots.
- b) Some core methodologies (e.g. visioning, PSDM, NbS selection framework) will be part of the planned actions in most pilots. However, the level of application of these methods (e.g. number of workshops where these methods are used) will vary from one pilot to another.
- c) Some synergies between these methods are identified to develop joint participatory activities to increase effectiveness of our action.

Therefore, these methodologies will be the building blocks in the design of the participatory processes, allowing a tailor-made design of these activities in each pilot to fully align and fit the participatory processes with the particular goals of the pilot and the general goals of the project.

A summary of each methodology, objectives, activities and necessary steps, implementation needs, and expected outputs and outcomes, is hereafter provided.

4.1. Visioning (WP2)

Led by: ECOADAPTA (Manuel Bea, Pedro Zorrilla Miras)

A. Introduction

The visioning methodology includes i) Developing a vision for a “business as usual” future; ii) Use of backcasting techniques to identify and think of actions, norms, policies and programs that could potentially connect the consensus visions for desirable futures with the present situation; iii) Assessment of LENSES results for consensus building on policy changes and the best potential for reaching the shared visions.

B. Objectives

The objectives are to identify the most important factors concerning the Nexus in each Pilot site, to build a shared desired future (vision), and to design a selection of interventions and policies necessary to arrive at the desired future (what we call “strategic roadmaps”).

The main objectives to obtain from the participatory action are to share views and objectives between different stakeholders, so that different stakeholders increase awareness about the WEF interconnections and about the legitimate interests of other stakeholders.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

- Identify main WEF challenges: Identification of the main problems relating to WEF, objectives for the pilot, drivers of change, temporal timeframe, e.g., 2030, 2040, 2100.
- To reach a shared vision: Participants have to define how they would like to be the Pilot area in the future.
- Backcasting exercise: Participants propose political and private initiatives along time to reach the desired objective or vision.
- Roadmaps/Pathways: Common set of interventions along time. Evaluation of the strategic roadmaps, and presentation of first results of the PSDM.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Timeline: in 1-3 workshops (depending on the level of interest of the Pilot leaders).
- Approximate time needed for each action/step: approx. 2-3 h per workshop.
- Min-Max people needed: minimum of 5 participants, maximum of 60.
- Stakeholders necessary to involve: stakeholder that represent different interests, e.g., farmers, local population, city council, regional government, scientists, protected areas technicians, NGOs.
- Materials: big maps, pens, paper and sticky notes. Option to use the [Nexus Game - Face the complexity of water-food-energy management \(socialsimulations.org\)](https://socialsimulations.org/).
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): workshop.

E. Expected outcomes

The expected outcome are LENSES strategic roadmaps for each pilot describing bundles of narratives, strategies and actions that support the achievement of the long-term desirable visions.

4.2. Participatory system dynamics model (PSDM) for scenario analysis (WP3)

Led by: IRSA (Alessandro Pagano and Raffaele Giordano)

A. Introduction

This methodology aims to engage stakeholders in developing a system dynamic model capable of mapping the complex web of interactions among the ecological resources, processes – both natural and human-induced – and pressures affecting the production and mobilization of the ecosystem services for the Nexus security dimensions. The final scope of the model is to support the discussion among the different stakeholders for co-designing, testing, and evaluating different intervention bundles for Nexus resilience building. Scenario analysis will be performed using both qualitative and quantitative PSDM tools to explore a wide range of conditions and a multiplicity of measures.

In the first phase, sectoral qualitative models – i.e., Causal Loop Diagram – will be developed based on the integration between the scientific and stakeholders’ knowledge. The analysis of these qualitative models will allow to identify the Nexus objectives and the main issues to be addressed for the Nexus resilience. A participatory exercise will be, then, organized with the scope of engaging stakeholders in the aggregation of the sectoral models. This will help identify in a participatory way key interconnections and mutual dependencies between different sectors, ultimately highlighting the main causal chains and the feedback loops that characterize system state and its potential evolution. The interactions among agents that are involved in resources management and ES production will be also explicitly investigated and modelled.

The quantitative PSDM will be used to consolidate individual/sectoral and cross-sectoral views of Nexus systems. The main physical processes will be described. The behaviours of actors will be explicitly introduced in the models and used to understand and describe the social processes behind the production and use of ES. The model’s capability to simulate future scenarios and the system dynamic evolution over the years will be used to support the visioning exercise (WP2).

B. Objectives

A comprehensive view of the Nexus system will be provided. PSDM tools will be used to co-develop a model useful to describe potential system evolution (with a focus on key variables and indicators) in the future, under different Nexus interventions. The future system pathways will be then discussed, and explicitly linked to the main SDGs for the pilot area.

Main objectives to obtain from the participatory action are collecting the stakeholders’ understanding of the main elements affecting the different dimensions of the Nexus security and resilience, and raise stakeholders’ awareness about the trade-offs among sectoral policies.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

The participatory actions will be developed primarily in two selected pilots - i.e. Doñana and Tarquinia. The experiences will be replicated with WP4 support in the other pilots. The participatory actions are:

- Targeted interviews (with a limited number of stakeholders) will be potentially used to clarify specific dynamics, connections, and feedback affecting sectoral securities.

- Activities oriented to facilitate the ‘Nexus dialogue’, and ultimately to collectively build/validate the conceptual model of the Nexus system under investigation.
- Social Mapping exercises will be also performed (using SNA techniques) to build and analyze the network of formal and informal interactions among the actors involved in Nexus management.
- The activity will also be oriented to the bottom-up identification and selection of key variables, then associated to relevant indicators derived from a literature review. Such indicators will be then used to describe more quantitatively system state and potential evolution, also through PSDM.
- Qualitative (CLDs) and quantitative (Stock and flow) SD models will be used, along with Agent Based Models, in the pilots. The specific approach will be selected according to the specificities of the pilot and to the specific contribution that WP4 will provide to the pilot. The WP4 team will be mainly involved in modelling activities (IRSA), and ask for a contribution of the pilot teams, mainly oriented to collect, structure, and compile the information needed for the model.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Timeline: in 2 workshops.
- Approximate time necessary: 3 h per workshop.
- Min-Max people needed: 30 people from different Nexus sectors.
- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: stakeholders responsible for the management of the ecological resources, beneficiaries of the ES, actors influencing the pressures on the ecological resources.
- Materials: geographical maps of the study areas, papers, and sticky notes.
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): semi-structured interviews and workshops.

E. Expected outcomes

Qualitative/Conceptual modelling of Nexus systems based on SDM techniques (CLD), for an improved understanding of Nexus system state and potential evolution under different actions. Scenario analysis will be also performed, and the results discussed with the stakeholders. A holistic framework and toolset for analysing scenarios in the pilot cases and to examine how policy choices across the WEF Nexus can influence wider progress in the delivery of the SDGs.

4.3. Mapping policy context and developing policy scenarios (WP4)

Led by: IRSA (Raffaele Giordano and Alessandro Pagano)

A. Introduction

Participatory mapping exercises will be applied to map the complex web of interactions among the different agents involved in the management of the resources for the Nexus security and resilience. The main goal is to detect barriers hampering the effective multi-level cooperation for a sustainable Nexus implementation, overcoming the “silo-base” approach in policy design and implementation. The results of this analysis will enable a stakeholders’ dialogue for co-design networking intervention, that is policies for enhancing the collaboration for the Nexus management. An Ecosystem Service (ES) based approach will be adopted for mapping the different interactions. The ES approach: i) tries to capture the Nexus interactions and governance deficits by analysing actors-ES network, ii) encourage negotiation and cooperation among ES users, iii) support the integration of fragmented institutional settings, iv) contribute to operationalizing the Nexus in terms of trade-offs and synergies, v) and facilitate the alignment between the governance framework and the ecological processes. Adopting an ES-based approach in the analysis of the socio-economic and institutional interactions means that actors are not linked exclusively through formal interactions. Informal - and often hidden - interactions happen in the biophysical system, e.g. using the same resources or competing for the ES. The work in LENSES is based on the assumption according to which trade-offs and conflicts among different agents in Nexus management are often caused by actors that are linked via interactions in the biophysical system (through ecological resources and processes), that have not appropriate correspondence in the network of socio-institutional interactions.

B. Objectives

This participatory action aims at engaging stakeholders in co-defining the socio-ecological and technical (SET) map, i.e. the map showing the interconnections among the socio-economic system, the ecological resources and processes and the different technological elements – i.e. infrastructures – needed for producing and mobilizing the ES. The socio-ecological network is centred around the ES of interests and, in a first step, uses ecological networks to identify which ecological resources and processes, directly and indirectly, contribute to the ES production and provision. In the ecological network, the nodes represent the ecological components - e.g. resources, species, etc. - and links describe the processes happening within the ecological network. The ecological network helps identify critical dependencies that affect ES. The social network can specify who benefits from an ES, which entities manage the services, and how those individuals and organizations interact. Moreover, in this work we also considered the stakeholders and decision-makers exerting pressure on the ecological resources needed for the ES production. Interactions within a social network influence the impacts of management actions on the ES provisioning. Moreover, social interactions influence knowledge exchange between different stakeholders involved in decisions, governance of natural resources, defining which policy objectives should be pursued. Finally, the interactions in the social networks determine how people value, use and demand different ES.

<p>C. Method description, activities, and steps</p> <p>The participatory actions to be developed in two selected pilots, i.e. Doñana and Tarquinia, and include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Round of semi-structured interviews for collecting stakeholders’ understanding about the SET network. ○ Analysis of the SET map and identification of the key barriers, validation with the stakeholders during the first workshop. ○ Network interventions co-design and simulation during the second workshop (policy scenario).
<p>D. What we need to implement the method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Timeline: two workshops. ○ Approximate time necessary: 1 h per workshop. ○ Min-Max people needed: 30 people from different Nexus sectors. ○ Stakeholders necessary to be involved: stakeholders responsible for the management of the ecological resources, beneficiaries of the ES, actors influencing the pressures on the ecological resources. ○ Materials: whiteboard for collecting stakeholders’ inputs. ○ Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): interviews and workshops.
<p>E. Expected outcomes</p> <p>Socio-ecological-technical map for Nexus management. Policy recommendations for enabling Nexus implementation in different socio-institutional contexts. Support to evidence-based policy design through scenarios.</p>

4.4. Nature-based solutions (NBS) selection framework (WP5)

Lead by: TUC (Nikolaos Nikolaidis and Maria A. Lilli)

A. Introduction

This methodology includes the identification of the potential role of NBS for addressing the challenges and opportunities for a resilient Nexus. It includes the analysis of the available methodologies and information requirements for assessing the technical effectiveness of individual NBS. A WEF Nexus-appropriate framework for evaluating options for increasing resilience was developed. A roadmap to help the pilots navigate the landscape was also produced.

B. Objectives

The objective of this methodology is to evaluate the WEF Nexus through the identification of the optimized NBS for addressing the challenges.

Main objectives to obtain from the participatory action is the optimization of the selected NBSs and the overcome of the barriers that will rise from their implementation.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

- **Develop a vision for the landscape in consultation with the local stakeholders.** The first phase of the methodology is the development of a vision for the landscape. This vision drives the project and the potential local stakeholders to achieve consensus and overcome the many barriers that will rise from its implementation. To develop such a vision, it is important to identify the environmental and ecological problems of the area to define a holistic approach for solving them that would give added value to the region and enhance its resilience. This vision brings local stakeholders and the decision-makers on board in order to materialize the project.
- **Identify the challenges the area/basin under consideration is facing regarding the Water-Ecosystem-Food Nexus.** These challenges can be viewed at this stage separately for each component of the Nexus.
- **Select WEF Nexus appropriate NBS bundles.** Use the list of Nexus appropriate NBS presented in the Annex and tables 4-10, developed in Deliverable 5.1 and select a primary list of appropriate NBS that address the vision for the landscape and the challenges.
- **Apply the WEF NEXUS Evaluation Framework.** Identify the desired ecosystem services to obtain from the landscape as well the approaches to use to improve. These selections should be consistent with the vision identified in the first step.
- **Evaluate the list of potentially applicable NBS** that contribute to more than one component of the WEF Nexus.
- **Identify related KPIs** for each NBS selected.
- **Conduct stakeholder consultation** (focus groups) on the selected WEF optimized NBSs
- **Revise list and follow the same steps until the NBS list that optimize the WEF Nexus is finalized**

D. What we need to implement the method

- Approximate time necessary: one day workshop
- Min-Max people needed: 5-10 people (focus expert group)
- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: focus group with local stakeholders (planners, decision makers, representative of users/ farmers)
- Materials: presentations with suggestions and lists of potentially applicable NBS
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): A structured discussion will be used as a method for decision-making. The Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats (SWOT) will be used as a decision-making tool to identify the best solutions to interdisciplinary and mostly qualitative alternatives. The results of SWOT analysis will be presented and discussed with the focus group. The final decisions will be revised according to their suggestions.

E. Expected outcomes

Decision makers and local stakeholders have access to an evidence-based framework and guidance to select solutions that incorporate nature-based approaches to increase the resilience of the WEF Nexus.

4.5. NBS business cases (WP6)

Led by: ETIFOR (Juan Diego Restrepo and Linda Barci)

A. Introduction

The Nature-based Solutions (NBS) Business Cases consist of a framework to help users (e.g., pilot leaders) develop business and governance models for the selected NBS, with a participatory approach. This kind of framework includes a business model canvas with different steps to follow, to define aspects such as the key partners, resources, activities, cost structure, and governance arrangements of the NBS to be developed. Some of these steps involve participatory activities to a greater or lesser extent.

The framework also includes elements for socio-economic and policy-enabling analyses for the selected NBS and relevant information related to financing options, investment, and existing business models for ensuring their sustainability.

B. Objectives

The objective is to develop business, financing, and governance models for the bundle of NBS selected from the Lenses pilot areas to plan and seek their long-term sustainability.

The main objectives of the participatory actions are to define, through a common understanding between stakeholders from different sectors (e.g., water management, agriculture), the key activities, resources, partners, and beneficiaries needed to implement the selected NBS, developing a shared vision and a sense of ownership of the process.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

The main steps involving stakeholders include:

- Defining the NBS's value proposition: Participants need to express how according to the identified Nexus challenges, the NBS is offering value from the environmental (e.g., addressing droughts), social (e.g., increased food security), and economic (e.g., job creation) perspectives. How to consider trade-offs between these perspectives?
- Delineating the value delivery of the NBS: Exercise to determine the key activities, resources, and partners needed and identify the key beneficiaries to implement the NBS effectively. In this phase, the activities related to determining the value capture of the NBS (e.g., cost structure, funding mechanisms) can be socialised and discussed with relevant stakeholders to get feedback from them.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Timeline: in 1-3 workshops (depending on the level of interest to the Pilot leaders).
- Approximate time necessary: approx. 2-3 h per workshop.
- Min-Max people needed: depending on the step of the business model canvas to develop. Some activities will need participation from large, heterogeneous groups (e.g., >15 participants), while others require shorter, more homogeneous ones (e.g., <5 participants).

- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: stakeholders representing different interests, e.g., farmers, local population, city council, regional government, scientists, protected areas technicians, NGOs.
- Materials: cardboards, pens, paper, and sticky notes.
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): depending on the type of stakeholders (knowledge, number, heterogeneity, motivation), activities such as focus groups, brainstorming, or world café can be carried out in the workshops. For the more technical parts of the canvas, consultations with experts can be made through interviews or the Delphi method.

E. Expected outcomes

The expected outcomes from these activities are that decision makers can arrive to NBS that are proactively designed to address socio-economic challenges and ready for implementation via sound business and governance models.

4.6. Climate risk assessments (WP7)

Led by DRAXIS (Christina Papadaskalopoulou and Marina Antoniadou)

A. Introduction

In the framework of the LENSES Project, a methodology was developed for the assessment of climate risks on the Water – Ecosystem – Food Nexus, based on the conceptual framework of the IPCC and of the World Bank. Specifically, for the assessment of climate risk a qualitative formula is used for depicting the relationship of risk with hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.

$$Risk = Hazard * Exposure * Vulnerability$$

Each variable of the above equation will be a composite indicator consisting of one or more sub-indicators. A set of **hazard** indicators will be used to reflect the climate dependent information for each impact and will be calculated with the use of information on the climate projections for climate-based indexes. **Exposure** will be estimated with the use of spatial data on landscape characteristics, such as land use/cover, agricultural land management, essential ecosystems, etc. Regarding the **vulnerability** aspect, a series of indices will be adopted for assessing the predisposition and susceptibility of certain critical elements of the Nexus sectors in climatic hazards.

Once the climate risk is estimated, adaptive capacity will be evaluated. In specific, for assessing adaptive capacity, the institutional capacity and the larger economic and social context are taken into account for assessing how these may influence the level of risk.

Climate Risk Assessment is designed so as to convey to the pilots' partners valuable information on the expected future climate and risks for the pilot areas. Therefore, the assessment focuses on the requirements of the pilot partners and of the local stakeholders, as the climate risk indicators will be selected based on their needs and tailored to the local conditions of the pilot areas. These indicators will be calculated based on different thresholds that will be set by the pilots' partners (e.g. for specific crops of high added value for the area), according to areas' unique characteristics.

B. Objectives

The objective of the activity is to collect feedback from pilot leaders in collaboration with stakeholders, in the following activities:

- **Selection of** for climate risk indicators as well as of their respective **critical thresholds where relevant** (e.g. optimum temperature range for the growth of high importance crops for the pilot area)
- **Weighting** individual risk indicators (e.g. hazard, exposure, sensitivity)
- **Evaluation of Institutional readiness** for adaptation at the pilot areas

C. Method description, activities, and steps

The participation of LENSES pilot partners along with the local stakeholders is of paramount importance for this procedure, as they have solid knowledge about the studied areas, and their inputs will contribute to a complete and informative estimation of climatic risk. The participatory actions to be developed in the selected pilots include:

- Selection of the climate risk indicators based on the needs of the pilot partners and local stakeholders and tailored to the local conditions of the pilot areas. These indicators will be calculated based on different thresholds that will be set by the pilot partners (e.g. for specific crops of high added value for the area), according to areas' unique characteristics.
- Weighting individual indicators for the development of composite indicators and assessing the overall impacts, with the participation of pilot's partners and stakeholders.
- Assessing the institutional adaptive capacity of the competent authorities at the pilot areas/regions. The assessment will focus on the evaluation of selected adaptive capacity components based on a set of criteria through a comprehensive questionnaire that will be developed specifically for that purpose.
 - First phase: Online table where the preferences will be recorded for each stakeholder with respect to the climate risk indicators and the respective thresholds.
 - Second phase: Online Questionnaire for weighting indicators and adaptive capacity components.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): Workshops and questionnaires.
- Timeline: As the deadline of the deliverable is in April 2023, we would like to take advantage of the workshops that will take place until January 2023, in order to better understand stakeholders' needs. Overall, we would need one meeting/workshop for each phase, in total two meetings/workshops. Approximately we plan the 1st phase to last until M16 (Sep 2022) and the 2nd phase until M21 (Jan 2023).
- Approximate time necessary: 45 minutes.
- Min-Max people needed: It is up to the pilot leaders to decide what is the optimum participation.
- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: It is up to the pilot leaders to decide what is the optimum participation.
- Materials: a projector and personal laptops/smartphones, to complete some online surveys during the meeting. However, this can take place also after the meeting, by each stakeholder individually.

E. Expected outcomes

Risk assessment tailored to the pilot areas needs and characteristics. The participation of REXUS pilot partners along with the local stakeholders is of paramount importance for this procedure, as they have solid knowledge about the studied areas, and their inputs will contribute to a complete and informative estimation of climatic risk.

4.7. Land use mapping & land use suitability (WP7)
Led by AGRISAT (Anna Osann, Llanos López, Esteban Henao)
A. Introduction
Maps of biogeophysical parameters derived from Earth Observation data will be developed in each pilot. Some of the potential products to be produced are yield potential and resource management indicators, including the use efficiency of water, nutrients, land, energy, and carbon footprint. Future land use suitability will be predicted under different scenarios of climate change. Finally, land suitability maps will be produced, indicating the optimum varieties as well as including guidelines for sustainable farming practices, land, and water management.
B. Objectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Establish a harmonised geodatabase highlighting soil and land quality indicators. ○ Analyse how land use and landscape management influence soil quality (including carbon and nutrient content) and groundwater, and develop a standard definition of prime quality soils. ○ Analyse good soil and land management methods, both conventional and innovative technologies. ○ Develop an assessment framework to evaluate current soil and quality and establish limiting factors for optimal land quality and productivity, (including heavy metal contamination). ○ Evaluate factors describing the weight of each soil quality indicator for land suitability (crop growth, meteorology, landscape, soil, water).
C. Method description, activities, and steps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Workshops and bilateral meetings to address land use issues. ○ Validation of results presenting NDVI and RGB Curves, methodologies, indicators and land use ranking (VS (Very suitable), S (Suitable), MS (Moderately suitable), mS (Marginally suitable), VmS (Very marginally suitable), NS (Not suitable)).
D. What we need to implement the method
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Timeline: 1-2 workshops and bilateral meetings / 2 hours each. ○ Min-Max people needed: AgriSat team (5), pilot teams (2-10). ○ Stakeholders not necessary to be involved, information can go through the pilot teams. ○ Materials: PPT's, AGRISAT webgis, Global Agro-Ecological Zone Model (GAEZv4).
E. Expected outcomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Crops Land Use for different years using Sentinel Scale (10 m). ○ Average NDVI curves for the main crops (agreed with stakeholders). ○ Creation of a replicable land use methodology. ○ Creation of Management Zone Maps (MZM), which are total or partial surfaces of a plot occupied by the same species and managed in a homogeneous way. In order to compare biomass values of each pixel with respect to the average value of the total crop unit.

4.8. Water accounting, allocation and planning (WP7)

Led by EA-TEK (Ali Gül, Filiz Barbaros, Gulay Onusluel, Cem Polat Cetinkaya)

A. Introduction

The need and the rationale behind developing this task is to understand the functioning of hydrological systems and how they respond to climate change and anthropogenic impacts. It is foreseen to be developed in 4 steps (depending on local methodological practice capacities, data quantity/quality/precision issues, other boundary conditions): (i) Carrying out water accounting at acceptable spatial and temporal resolutions, (ii) Establishing sectoral water demands as well as evaluating associated priorities, (iii) Performing water balance simulations in order to examine sectoral (irrigation, environmental, energy, urban) water allocation policies/practices as “business as usual” versus “Nexus targeted” approach. (iv) Planning water resources based on an adaptation framework.

B. Objectives

The objectives are to (1) identify/assess prevailing pilot-specific water supply security problems against sectoral competitions, (2) unfold trends/alterations in water availability under changing environmental conditions (considering climate and land-driven changes), (3) (re)orienting/testing policy interventions under current/simulated conditions.

Among the main objectives to obtain from the participatory action are (i) proper identification of the pilot-specific problems, (ii) better representative set-up of water accounting model(s), (iii) data mining and compilation for precise uses, (iv) identifying sectoral demands, bottlenecks and competitions for water, (v) validation of simulation outputs, and (vi) developing scenario simulations under changing climatic and land-use conditions.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

- Identification workshops for addressing water-supply problems, sectoral demands, emerging trends in water competition under non-stationary conditions.
- Validating hydrologic simulations under current and future scenario conditions.
- Tailoring water allocation simulations by employing altered water availability figures under non-stationary future conditions.
- Addressing foreseen/expected/suggested policy interventions that fundamentally relate to water allocation schemes between the sectors involved.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Timeline: 1-3 workshops per pilot.
- Approximate time necessary: approx. 2-3 h per workshop.
- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: stakeholders from water governance frameworks (water authorities, national/regional/local administrations), water dependent sector representatives (water user associations, wetland managers, industry representatives, drinking water supply responsables, etc.), academics, relevant NGOs, SME partners involved in water business.

- Materials: Presentations, trial simulations, workshop stationery items (pens, boards, board markers, sticky notes, etc.)
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): Workshops, questionnaires, participatory mapping actions (hand-written schematic mapping/sketching exercises to serve for problem identification).

E. Expected outcomes

Water availability/allocation figures (potentially through computed indicator variables and/or spatial summary statistics) to feed into policy perspectives analyses and systems dynamics modelling experiments.

4.9. Linking Nexus management to SDG delivery (WP7)

Led by DRAXIS: (M. Antoniadou, C.Papadaskalopoulou, E. Ntzioni, E. Chatzitheodorou)

A. Introduction

Working in those pilot areas which require most progress across the SDGs, the PSDM will be used to provide information both on fluxes in critical resource stocks over time and across different scales required to meet specific targets across the wide spectrum of SDGs. An assessment of how different policy interventions under a range of future scenarios will consolidate into a simulation serious game, through which decision makers and other stakeholders can explore the wider influence of policy options. The serious game will visualize the PSDM, but this exercise will not focus on the content of the PSDM but on the functionality of the game.

B. Objectives

- Examination of how policy choices under a range of future scenarios across the Water- Ecosystem-Food Nexus can influence wider progress in the delivery of the SDGs.
- Development of an easy-to-access simulation serious game (the Nexus-SDG toolkit) through which relevant stakeholders and the wider public can explore the influence and implications of policy decisions on SDGs.
- The ultimate goal of the serious game is to aid learning, through an interactive capacity-building tool for exploring the concept and value of the synergies among SDGs and policy choice.

C. Method description, activities, and steps

The participatory actions to be developed in the selected pilots include the presentation of a draft first version of the serious game and to ask from the stakeholders to evaluate it and to provide suggestions for improvement through a short questionnaire. It will not be possible to play with the game as at that time the game will be not fully functional. So there will be a presentation of the conceptual approach of the game where participants will be called to evaluate the envisaged functionalities of the tool and to define user needs and requirements.

D. What we need to implement the method

- Timeline: Between M22-M27, ~3 pilot workshops in total.
- Approximate time necessary: 30-45 min.
- Min-Max people needed: 10-30 people.
- Stakeholders necessary to be involved: all types of stakeholders.
- Materials: a projector for presenting the serious game. Personal laptops/smartphones, in order to complete some online surveys.
- Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): Questionnaire.

E. Expected outcomes

Design of a serious game well-fitting to stakeholder needs, user-friendly, comprehensive, and educational.

4.10. Story as a driver of change (WP9)
Led by AGRISAT (Anna Osann, Esteban Henao, Llanos López)
A. Introduction
Storytelling will: (a) raise awareness on the problems (storytelling at the initiation of the project); (b) support knowledge management (stories will be shared among participants of LAAs); (c) enhance the dissemination of the LENSES approach and results (success stories from case studies and their impact to inspire replication and scaling up of solutions piloted, disseminated to diverse audiences to instigate mind shift and change). Stories will be created in various forms: interviews, narratives adaptable in size, podcasts, and short videos.
B. Objectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Raise awareness of the Nexus issues, communicate the message using a particular type of narrative targeting different society actors, and build a strong connection of actors from different domains of the Nexus. ○ Improve the dissemination of the LENSES approach and results. ○ Create stories that allow us to compile complex information and transmit it simply and understandably. ○ Share our LENSES story and previous experiences that have evaluated the Nexus and tell our own story of what led us to analyse the Nexus.
C. Method description, activities, and steps
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Telling stories among all participants, open spaces to share experiences. ○ To insist on the need to share our experiences with society at large through social networks and our website. ○ To make an appeal to the actors who need to get involved through easily understandable informative documents.
D. What we need to implement the method
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Timeline: Maybe one workshop, if necessary (2 hours per workshop). ○ Min-Max people needed: If this activity is to be shared in a workshop, the more people the better. ○ Stakeholders necessary to be involved: minimum 10 people. ○ Materials: people to share their experiences. ○ Basic structure or method to use (interviews, workshop, questionnaire, etc.): Questionnaires, fact sheets, brochures and a fundamental point are the interviews, which can have a very high impact.
E. Expected outcomes
Set of successful Nexus stories

5. DESIGN OF THE PARTICIPATORY PROCESSES IN THE LENSES PILOTS

5.1. Overall design

According to the Grant Agreement, “Several workshops and activities will be combined with a series of five LAA Meetings (“Regional Meetings”) aimed at discussing the main Nexus issues, visions, conflicts, gaps and needs, and setting the basis for social and institutional cross-sectoral contracts for integrated and sustainable Nexus management that outlive the project. These activities will follow an iterative sequence through which stakeholders advance in the process towards reaching consensus visions for addressing Nexus trade-offs.”

Through a number of online meetings with the LENSES pilots, the following structure (see figure 2) has been suggested for the organisation of the five Regional Meetings:

- An initial LAA kick-Off meeting to introduce the LENSES project and the main pilot challenges and aims to the main stakeholders. It must be noted that in some pilots this meeting has been substituted by face to face or online presentations mainly due to uncertainty derived from the Covid-19 pandemic.
- Three workshops for co-development and progress of the LENSES methodologies in the pilots.
- A final workshop/wrap-up meeting with a focus on the legacy of the LAA action.

Moreover, many activities not involving the broader group of stakeholders (e.g. interviews, focus groups, expert consultation, seminars) can be organised between the workshops.

5 “Regional Meetings” (tentative timeline and content)

Figure 2. Suggested timeline and content for the five Regional Meetings

5.2. Initial matchmaking between pilots and methods

The application of the methodologies of LENSES supporting WEF Nexus analysis and operationalisation into practice will differ across LENSES pilots, i.e. not all methodologies are going to be applied in detail everywhere. Furthermore, not all methodologies will use participatory methods in all LENSES pilots. Thus, each pilot will consider the methodologies applied and which ones will be applied using participatory methods, to organise their work and, therefore, their participatory processes through the LAA Meetings (“Regional Meetings”).

Some support to this matchmaking process has been undertaken through:

- a) Initial exchanges in the LENSES Kick-Off meeting.
- b) A series of follow-up meetings organised for each pilot in the context of WP8, with attendance of all the Task leaders developing methodologies, and focusing on identifying the main challenges and Nexus objectives and specifying what methods can contribute to answer the pilot’s needs.
- b) An online survey prepared by WP2 where all pilots were asked about their interests in implementing each of the LENSES methodologies, and whether this potential implementation needs to include participatory aspects.

Initial results of this matchmaking process are registered in Table 1.

Table 1. Initial matchmaking between LENSES pilot sites, the methodologies applied in each of them, and which ones will be applied using participatory methods. Numbers indicate the pilots’ interest and feasibility in the application of each method to help address their key challenges (5= High interest; 1= Low interest). Colours indicate to what extent the pilots are interested in applying the methodologies using participatory approaches. [Green = Yes, White = Maybe, Grey = Not really]

LENSES methodologies supporting WEF Nexus analysis and operationalisation into practice in each pilot site										
	Visions	PSDM	Policy Perspective	NBS selection	NBS business cases	Climate risk assessments	Land Use Mapping	Water accounting	Nexus SDGs	Story-telling
Doñana	5	5	4	2	2	4	1	5	2	4
Gediz	2	4	1	5	1	5	3	5	1	5
Hula Valley	5	2	4	2	4	5	4	5	5	3
Koiliaris	4	4	2	5	5	2	5	2	2	1
Deir Alla	2	5	4	5	3	4	4	5	4	4
Pinios	4	3	2	5	4	3	5	4	1	3
Tarquinoa	5	5	5	1	1	5	5	4	5	4

As a result, from this analysis, we come to know that:

- ✓ All methods are willing to be applied following a participatory format.
- ✓ All methods are planned to be applied in a participatory way in at least two pilots, and as much as in five of the pilots.
- ✓ There is not a single method that is clearly rejected to be applied in a participatory format.
- ✓ All pilot sites are planning to apply at least three methods in a participatory way.
- ✓ Each pilot has a clear idea that between one to three methods are not planned to be applied in a participatory format.

5.3. Design of the participatory process in each pilot

As a result of this matchmaking process, each pilot team will be able to advance on the overall design of the participatory process, i.e. selecting the methods and participatory tools to be applied along time.

Key participatory activities with local stakeholders will be bundled in the workshops. Moreover, some participatory activities can integrate requirements from different methodologies for a more effective participation, so that a single participatory action can be useful for the development of more than one of the LENSES methodologies.

Our recommendation for the pilot leaders is:

- 1) To identify those core methodologies that aim to produce strong contributions to help identify and cope with the most relevant challenges at the pilot scale through a systemic Nexus approach. These core methodologies should be fully applied in the pilot with the broader group of stakeholders (i.e. being part of the series of workshops).
- 2) To look for synergies and common points between these core methodologies towards the organisation of participatory activities producing meaningful inputs for different core methods.
- 3) To analyse what other methodologies (i.e. additional methodologies) can be co-implemented through participatory approaches to complement the results or even feed to the core methodologies. Participatory activities dealing with these additional methodologies can be included in the workshops or conducted through specific activities within the frame of the LAAs, not necessarily involving to the broader group of stakeholders.

As an example, a tentative design of the participatory activities for the Doñana pilot is described in figure 3. As shown in table 1, visioning, policy analysis and the construction of the PSDM are core activities with a strong participatory background. Synergies between these three methodologies are exploited in the first workshop through the preparation of a participatory mapping exercise building from information collected through the initial round of interviews. Other additional activities will be either conducted as part of the workshops or through dedicated activities in the frame of the LAAs involving a shorter group of stakeholders, i.e. those with a higher interest of stronger expertise in that particular topic.

INCEPTION PHASE	WORKSHOP#1(WWS#1) Participatory mapping	WORKSHOP#2 Backcasting/Forecasting exercise	WORKSHOP#3 Validation of nexus roadmap
a) Interviews with key stakeholders from different nexus domains to identify main WEF challenges and objectives / detect barriers and key variables b) Apply NBS selection framework and select NBS bundles	a) Reach a systemic view on nexus challenges, key variables and barriers b) Clarify dynamics and connections c) Consensus on visions d) Governance mapping	a) Backcasting exercise building on results from WS#1 b) Use of the PSDM to validate most probable scenarios against desired futures. c) Elaboration of strategic roadmaps d) PEA analysis	a) Validation of the PSDM model b) Consensus on strategic roadmaps c) List of foreseen/expected/suggested policy interventions

ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

Selection of climate risk indicators	Validation of NBS bundles
Delineating value delivery of NBS and planning their value capture	Validating hydrologic simulation and tailoring water allocation simulations
Weighting climate risk indicators and assessing adaptive capacity	Feedback on the serious game

Figure 3. Tentative planning of participatory activities for Doñana pilot.

A final design of the participatory process will be integrated into the implementation roadmap of each pilot. It must be noted that WP8 is in charge of leading the actions on the pilots areas, serving as an interface between the other WPs and the pilots. WP2 and WP8 are intertwined and maintain regular contact to ensure a proper coordination between participatory activities in the pilots (WP2) and full implementation of LENSES in the pilots (WP8).

6. FINAL REMARKS AND NEXT STEPS

This Deliverable 2.1 contains basic guidelines to help pilot teams to develop a successful stakeholder engagement process along LENSES. It also has the aim to help to coordinate the participatory actions in all LENSES pilots, facilitating that they follow a similar process and approach.

This document contains the conceptual basis that will guide the LENSES stakeholder engagement process, the participatory actions, and the development of the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) in each Pilot. This deliverable also contains the necessary tools to initiate the stakeholder process and a compilation of all the LENSES methods for creating a Nexus systemic approach that will be applied in a participatory way. This catalogue of participatory methods will help the pilots to better understand each method, so that they can better plan its implementation.

The document also presents a table with the current plans of each pilot team, indicating what methods are they planning to apply in their pilot, and which of them are planned to be implemented using participatory tools. Then, **the next step is to design a participatory plan or road map for each pilot**, planning what tools and methods will be applied along the project and in each of the participatory workshops. This step will be led by each pilot team, although WP2 partners will help and facilitate this process. A direct interaction between the pilot teams and the partners leading the development of each LENSES method will be necessary for finalizing each pilot participatory plan or participatory road map. This can be implemented via email exchange and/or virtual meetings. Section 5.3 provides suggestions to design the participatory plan or road maps, and an example for the Doñana pilot.

Finally, the deliverable contains as an annex several supporting documents for the stakeholder engagement process, e.g. a catalogue of methodologies and event formats for the dynamization and facilitation of workshops, with the aim of serving as reference and help to the pilot teams that will develop the participatory actions.

This publication reflects only the author's view and the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Annex 1

RESULTS FROM THE STAKEHOLDER MAPPING EXERCISE IN EACH PILOT SITE

LENSES pilot teams have already followed the provided “stakeholder mapping” guidelines, and their results are included in this section. The key stakeholders have been identified by nexus domains, and the following codes have been used to identify the type of stakeholders:

[POL] Decision-makers and policy-makers

[USER] Association of end-users (e.g. farmers) or individual end-users

[CIT] Citizens, NGOs,

[EXP] Individual expert

[COM] Private companies

[RES] Research and academia

The current level of engagement of each stakeholder in LENSES project has been indicated in colors according to the following legend:

Legend	Contacted and already engaged in participatory activities	Contacted but still not engaged in participatory activities	Still not contacted
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Stakeholder mapping in Doñana (Spain)

Table I.1. Initial list of stakeholders in Doñana pilot

PILOT NAME: DOÑANA			
KEY STAKEHOLDERS	NEXUS DOMAIN		
	WATER	ECOSYSTEMS	FOOD
	W1: Guadalquivir River Basin Authority – water planning unit [POL]	E1: Andalucía Regional Government - Environment [POL]	F1: Andalucía Regional Government - Agriculture [POL]
	W2: Irrigators Association [USER]	E2: WWF [CIT, USER]	F2: Farmers’ Union - ASAJA [USER]
	W3: Irrigation consulting firm [COM]	E3: Ecological restoration Experts [EXP]	F3: IFAPA (regional agro-research institute) [RES]
	W4: Spain Geological Survey [RES]	E4: Doñana Biological Station [RES]	F4: Agriculture policy and management Experts [EXP]
	W5: Water policy Experts [EXP]	E5: Eco-tourism [COM/CIT]	F5: ZITRUS project [RES/USER]
	W6: Guadalquivir River Basin Authority – water use monitoring unit [POL]	E6: Doñana Natural Space [POL]	F6: SAI platform (association of EU large food retailers) [USER]
	W7: MITECO (Spain Ministry on environment) [POL]	E7: Experts in ESs and scenarios [RES/EXP]	F7: Farming companies (middle size) [COM]
	E8: Associations for Doñana preservation [CIT]	F8: Individual farmers [USER]	
		F9: CSIC-IRNAS (national research council – irrigation in woody crops) [RES]	

Figure I.1: Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria in Doñana.

Stakeholder mapping in Hula Valley pilot (Upper Galilee, Israel)

The Hula Valley pilot is located in the Upper Galilee of Israel and is based on the activities of the 35 Kibbutzim in the Galilee, which is a very special structure of organisations and relationship between them. In addition, there is a tight contact with the Upper Galilee regional Council – the municipality, which also only includes Kibbutzim. The Kibbutzim are organized in a cooperation – Galilee Developing Company, which establish and partially own the food processing industries in the Galilee.

All those entities are in contacts with MIGAL, which is also owned by the Galilee Developing Company. In the table below we will try to classify our stakeholders, with whom we are continuously in contact.

Table I.2. Initial list of stakeholders in Hula Valley pilot, Galilee.

PILOT NAME: Hula Valley				
KEY STAKEHOLDERS	NEXUS DOMAIN			
	WATER	ECOSYSTEMS	ENERGY	FOOD
	W1: Upper Galilee Regional Council [POL]	E1: Upper Galilee Regional Council [POL]	D1: MIGAL (RES)	F1: Upper Galilee Regional Council [POL]
	W2: 35 Kibbutzin [USER]	E2: Galilee Developing Company (POL and COM)	D2: Anagal (COM)	F2: Galilee Agricultural Company [USER]
	W3: Kolhi Galil Elion [COM]	E3: MIGAL [RES]	D3: Kibbutzim (USER)	F3: MIGAL [RES]
	W4: MIGAL [RES]	E4: Natural Parks and Nature Reserves [NGO]	D4: Agri-Light (COM)	F4: Galilee Development Company [COM]
	W5: Maim BaGalil [COM]	E5: Tourism NGO [CIT]	Dorel (COM)	F5: Avocado Gal [COM]
	W6: Galilee Agricultural Company [USER]	E6: Society for Protection of Nature [NGO]		F6: Of-HaGalil [COM]
	W7: Pituach HaGalil [POL]			F7: Pri HaGalil [COM]
	W8: Mai Tanur (COM)			F8: MilBar [COM]
W9: Peleg HaGalil (COM)				

Figure I.2: Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria in Hula Valley pilot, Galilee.

Stakeholder mapping in Tarquinia (Italy)

Table I.3. Initial list of stakeholders in Tarquinia pilot, along the WEF nexus domains.

PILOT NAME: TARQUINIA			
KEY STAKEHOLDERS	NEXUS DOMAIN		
	WATER	ECOSYSTEMS	FOOD
	W1: Water User Associations “Consorzio di Bonifica Litorale Nord” (CBLN) [EXP]	E1: LIPU Environmental Association [EXP]	F1: Individual farmers [USER]
	W2: Land Management Local Authority - Tarquinia Municipality [POL]	E2: Regional Environment Protection Agency [POL]	F2: Farming companies (middle size) [COM]
	W3: FATIMA research project [RES]	E3: Tourism and cultural heritage Local Authority - Tarquinia Municipality [POL]	F3: Farmers’ associations [POL]
		E4: Local Associations for Environmental and Land preservation [CIT, USER]	F4: Agricultural policy and management Local Authority - Tarquinia Municipality [POL]
		E5: Nature Reserve Salina di Tarquinia [RES]	F5: Regional Agency for Agriculture Innovation (ARSIAL) [RES, EXP]

Figure I.3: Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria in Tarquinia pilot.

Stakeholder mapping in Pinios (Greece)

Table I.4. Initial list of stakeholders in Pinios pilot.

PILOT NAME: PINIOS			
KEY STAKEHOLDERS	NEXUS DOMAIN		
	WATER	ECOSYSTEMS	FOOD
W1: Executive Water Directorate of Thessaly Water District [POL]	E1: Management Body of Karla – Mavrovouni – Kefalovriso – Velestino – Delta Piniou [POL]	F1: Farmer of Kiwi fruit, Head of Pirgetos farmers cooperative [USER]	
W2: Deputy Mayor of Tempi Municipality [POL]	E2: Deputy Mayor of Environment, Rural Development and Fisheries of Agia Municipality [POL]	F2: Directorate of Agricultural Economy of Thessaly Region [POL]	
W3: Directorate of Planning and Management of Water Services, General Directorate of Water, Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy [POL]	E3: Member of the Department of EU Projects of Agia Municipality [POL]	F3: Farmer and stock-breeder [USER]	
W4: Professor of Hydrology and Water Resources, Department of Rural and Surveying Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki [RES]	E4: Forester, Directorate of Environment and Spatial Planning of the region of Larissa [POL]	F4: Farmer in Agia Municipality [USER]	
W5: Department of Hydro-Economics and supervision Local Organizations of Land Reclamation, Thessaly’s Regional Organization of Land Reclamation [POL]	E5: Greek Biotope/Wetland Centre [RES]	F5: Agronomist in Agia Municipality [POL]	

		F6: Farmer of kiwi fruit, Irrigation network manager of Evrimeni [USER]
		F7: Director of Vocational School [RES]
		F8: Agronomist and farmer of apples and cherries [USER]
		F9: Piraeus Bank – Department of agricultural development [COM]
		F10: Farmers cooperative [USER]
		F11: Farmer
		F12: Professor of Agronomy, Department of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Environment, University of Thessaly [RES]
		F13: General Directorate of Agriculture, Hellenic Ministry of Rural Development and Food [POL]

Figure I.4: Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria in Pinios pilot.

Stakeholder mapping in Deir-Alla Pilot (Jordan)

Key stakeholders for Deir-Alla Pilot:

1. For the water sector in Jordan, the Ministry of Water and Irrigation and the Jordan Valley Authority are recommended to represent the public sector. Representatives of the Water Users Associations represent the agricultural water users in the consultations.
2. Of the NGOs in Jordan, Eco Peace Middle East has developed various water-related initiatives in the Valley and therefore represents the voluntary sector. Four WUA representatives in the Forum's Steering Committee have represented all WUAs in the consultation process during this Jordan Valley NGO Master Plan preparation.
3. The Ministry of Agriculture, NARC, and ACC represents the public sector for agricultural stakeholders in Jordan. Jordanian Farmers' Unions and the Fruits and Vegetables Association represents private sector institutions.
4. The Jordan Environment Society works on the tensions between economic and ecological issues concerning irrigated agriculture among the environmental NGOs.
5. The Directorates of Agricultural Services and Soil and Water Management of the Ministry of Agriculture are the primary public service providers for irrigated agriculture.

Table I.5. Stakeholders representing the Jordanian Water Sector.

Sectors	Formal Organizations that have been identified as representatives of stakeholder’s groups	Groupings involved in the Jordan Valley NGO master plan initiatives
Public sector	Ministry of Water and Irrigation; Jordan Valley Authority;	MoWI and WUAs participate in the Jordan Valley Water Forum that the World Bank Institute facilities
Private sector	Water Users Associations;	
Voluntary sector	EcoPeace Middle East Jordan Valley network	Women organization that represents the women as stakeholder in water and environmental services in the residential areas of the Jordan Valley

Table I.6. Stakeholders representing the Jordanian Agriculture Sector.

Sectors	Formal Organizations that have been identified as representatives of stakeholder’s groups	Groupings involved in the Jordan Valley NGO master plan initiatives
Public sector	-Ministry of Agriculture; National Agricultural Research Center (NARC); Agricultural Credit Corporation.	
Private sector	-Jordan Farmers Union; Irbid and Southern Shouneh Chambers of Commerce; Fruits and Vegetables Exporters Association.	Representatives of El Wakid, El Ghezawi and El Adwan clans representing the Al Ghawama family farmers. Grouping of LEISA family farms that has as objectives to promote environment-friendly agriculture production technologies in the JORDAN VALLEY.

Table I.7. Stakeholders representing the Jordanian Recreation and Environmental Sectors.

Sector	Formal Organizations that have been identified as representatives of stakeholder’s groups
Public sector	-Ministry of Tourism; Ministry of Environment.
Private sector	-Sothern Shouneh Chamber of Commerce; Dead Sea Tourism Board.
Voluntary sector	-EcoPeace Middle East Amman Office; Jordan Hashemite Fund for Human Development (JOHUD); Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature; Jordan Environmetal Society Jordan Valley Branch.

Table I.8. Initial list of stakeholders in Deir-Alla Pilot (Jordan).

PILOT NAME: Deir-Alla			
KEY STAKEHOLDERS	NEXUS DOMAIN		
	WATER	ECOSYSTEMS	FOOD
	W1: Ministry of Water and Irrigation [POL]	E1: Ministry of Environment [POL]	F1: Ministry of Water and Irrigation [POL]
	W2: Jordan Valley Authority [POL]	E2: Jordan Valley Authority [POL]	F2: Jordan Valley Authority [POL]
	W3: Water User Associations [USER]	E3: National Agricultural Research Center [RES]	F3: Water User Associations [USER]
	W4: National Agricultural Research Center [RES]	E4: Ministry of Agriculture [POL]	F4: National Agricultural Research Center [RES]
	W5: Ministry of Agriculture [POL]	E5: Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature [CIT]	F5: Ministry of Agriculture [POL]
	W6: EcoPeace Middle East [COM]	E6: EcoPeace Middle East [COM]	F6: EcoPeace Middle East [COM]
	W7: Technology providers [COM]		F7: Technology providers [COM]

Figure I.5: Stakeholder classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria in Deir-Alla Pilot (Jordan).

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Annex 2

Initial guidelines to support the activity of local Learning and Action Alliances

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Initial guidelines to support the activity of local Learning and Action Alliances

Version 0.0	27/07/2021
Dissemination level:	Restricted
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SUMMARY AND AIMS

This is an internal document to support the organisation of the initial meeting of the Local Learning and Action Alliances in the LENSES Pilots.

This template will be improved with the feedback collected after the meetings in the different pilots (e.g. what went well, what could be amended) and later distributed to the other Pilot areas involved in LENSES for the organisation of their initial meetings under a common framework.

The document contains a number of sections that can be distributed in advance as standalone briefs or as an introduction package to the participants in the meeting:

- a general introduction to LENSES project
- a general introduction to the Local Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) (i.e. challenges, aims, proposed structure)
- introduction to the local LAA
- an overview of the methods to be applied in each pilot, i.e. Pilot narrative and goals

Annex 1 provides specific suggestions for the organisation of the meeting, including some specific requirements from WP2, WP3 and WP4.

Annex 2 contains an overview of the LENSES pilots. This is relevant for the participants of the local LAAs because knowledge exchange between all the LENSES pilots are planned to be organised throughout the project.

THE LEARNING AND ACTION ALLIANCES IN LENSES

By Learning and Action Alliance (LAA) we mean a social infrastructure under the form of discussion-and-action groups composed of a broad selection of stakeholders (leading to increased trust and understanding of one another) that will iteratively convene through a structured series of workshops, participatory activities and discussion meetings with the aim to create communities in which learning resulting from project activities and outputs is directly translated into real action by the affected actors. This concept builds on other approaches for collective action and stakeholder engagement such as the ‘communities of practice’ (defined as a frame for studying how people learn socially from their peers within communities of a certain practice), and the ‘policy labs’, and adds a co-development and innovation component inspired in the ‘communities of innovation’. The main differentiating element considered in LENSES LAAs is the focus on social learning as a central element to facilitate Nexus Thinking and drive Resilient Nexus Doing. Most importantly, it must be kept in mind that a LAA is a dynamic learning process and a living collective body that is expected to evolve by trust-building among partners and common achievements.

The LENSES LAAs aim to help address one particular challenge: the lack of communication, coordination and dialogue between WEF nexus related stakeholders at multiple levels as well as silo thinking and acting have been acknowledged since the beginning of the Nexus movement as one of the main causes of conflict as well as core challenges and barriers for an effective WEF nexus management. When adding climate change to the equation, the challenges become more transversal and the trade-offs are exacerbated, making this dialogue and coordination even more critical.

The LAAs aim to overcome this challenge by providing a virtual and safe space for dialogue with all relevant stakeholders that can be uptaken by the stakeholders themselves to establish a governance mode for implementation and monitoring of the designed roadmaps, i.e. enhancing institutional and governance capacity for Nexus-doing. LENSES’ LAA platform and guidelines for the creation and operation of LAAs will provide the tools to create a social window of successful knowledge and action examples on Nexus resilient action with possibility to maintain a living network with capacity to grow and maintain operability and interconnection.

LENSES will bring together project partners and external stakeholders to facilitate co-learning and co-development in the frame of a 3-tiered scheme of LAAs:

- (1) **At local level** (Pilot scale), the LAAs gather relevant local stakeholders to generate cross-fertilisation of knowledge (i.e. exchange of different types of knowledge) and to validate and support the exploitation of the tools and methods generated by LENSES.
- (2) **At intra-project level**, one LAA provides mutual learning and knowledge exchange between the pilots’ stakeholders to address transferability (i.e. the ability to transfer/adopt in a given pilot area the successful measures previously adopted elsewhere, and achieve comparable results) and to exchange on barriers and drivers for the successful project implementation.
- (3) **At trans-project level**, one LAA enables knowledge transfer between LENSES and other projects, networks and institutions.

The Local Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) aim to address our challenge by facilitating the engagement of:

- ‘researchers’ (innovators / research centers) and
- ‘non-researchers’ (public management bodies / civil society / NGOs / end-users of natural resources)

to support the better understanding of challenges and the identification of systemic solutions to increase resilience and sustainable management of Nexus systems.

The role of the local LAAs in LENSES goes beyond the traditional approach where non-researchers are given an inactive role, i.e. merely considered as “data-providers” and/or “end-users”. The local LAAs aim to create a long-term collaborative atmosphere at pilot level, increase the knowledge exchange between local stakeholders and support the integration of stakeholder knowledge into the development of the solutions. This approach aims to achieve a **“win-win” collaboration to overcome the barrier from innovation to practice.**

ORGANISATION OF THE LENSES INTRODUCTION MEETING (AT PILOT SCALE)

Based on the list of topics identified in previous meetings with Pilot leaders and some Work Package leaders, the following tentative agenda is suggested¹:

Presentations	Content	Extent
Presentation 1 (P1): Welcome from Pilot Leader	Welcome and overall presentation of LENSES (objectives of the project, methods to be used and expected results)	(15 min)
P2: Presentation by the session moderator	Agenda and main aims for the meeting	(5 min)
P3: Overview of the Pilot: aims and challenges	Explanation of the general goals and action plan for the Pilot activities	(15 min)
P4: Concept of Learning and Action Alliances	What is a LAA? How we intend to manage the Local LAA (e.g. meeting every six months, organising a full day workshop per year, etc...?)	(5 min)
ROUNDTABLE	Description	Extent
Topic 1 (T1): 'Tour de table'	Short presentation of all participants, including main expectations for LENSES	(5-10 min)
T2: Setting objectives	What can LENSES do for me? What can I do for LENSES? Most important research needed in the area	(15 min)
T3: Stakeholder mapping	Mapping key stakeholders (Who do you miss in this room?).	(15 min)
T4: Grading the key challenges in the pilot	Which are the main challenges?	(15 min)

This internal document aims to evolve into a template to help the facilitator structure his/her presentations for the first local LAA panel meeting in all pilots involved in LENSES. This template will be modified accordingly with the feedback received after the initial meetings in the LENSES pilot areas.

Hereafter, some suggestions for the content of slides to include in the PowerPoint slide shows as well as for the moderation of the discussions in the roundtable, are provided.

PRESENTATIONS

P1.- WELCOME FROM NATIONAL ORGANIZER

15 minutes. Presentation given by Pilot leader

- Appreciation for coming
- Introduce the project
- Importance of the LENSES project
- Importance of stakeholder involvement for LENSES
- How we will be using the results

¹ NOTE: This is only a suggestion and please feel free to organise the meeting as you feel more convenient.

- Hopes for consultation

- *Appreciation for coming*
Welcome participants and thank them for coming to take part in this activity, part of LENSES project. Present shortly the partner organisation, the institution you come from, and explain that LENSES is conducted by a group of 13 partners, from 7* countries across the Mediterranean region with demo activities in seven pilot areas.
- *Introduction to LENSES and importance of the project*
Short overview of LENSES (brief description of the project key challenges and goals)
Why is this project important for the European Commission? (short remark)
- *Importance of stakeholder involvement*
This information is included in the Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines
- *Use of results*
The feedback collected from the meetings or activities conducted by the local LAA will exclusively be used to support the progress of the project.
This feedback may be communicated to
 - other project partners, i.e. partners leading activities in the technical work packages
 - the European Commission, as part of two internal documents that we are entitled to deliver by the middle and end of the project to report on the work done by the LENSES LAAs.The feedback will be attributed to the organisations participating in the activities and not to individual persons.
Specific permission will be asked for the external dissemination of any images or specific information related to LENSES meetings or activities.
- *Hopes for the local LAA*
“It is our sincere hope that you will have a very nice time at this meeting.
“We hope that this LAA contributes to expand the dialogue about how ***.”

P2.- WELCOME FROM MODERATOR

5 minutes. Presentation given by Session moderator

- Agenda
- Ground rules for the meeting

- *Agenda*

Present agenda for the meeting:

- *Ground rule for the meeting (rules for dialogue)*

We have a common understanding about:

- There are no right or wrong answers – there are many possible realities → all contributions and perspectives are appreciated.
- Our goal is to build a “win-win” collaboration between research and practical knowledge. This implies a two-way collaboration.
 - Stakeholders are asked to:
 - i) Provide support to the development of LENSES methods
 - ii) Identify how LENSES can provide support to them
- We are ready to let go of our own determinations and find a broad consensus

P3.- OVERVIEW OF THE PILOT: AIMS AND CHALLENGES

15 minutes. Presentation given by Pilot leader

- Specification of the key objectives and identification of main challenges
- Description of activities planned in the pilot

P4.- CONCEPT OF LEARNING AND ACTION ALLIANCES

5 minutes. Presentation given by Session moderator

- Concept of local LAAs in LENSES
- Next steps

- *The concept of Local Community of Practice in LENSES*

Definition of LAA.

Two key aspects:

- Main aim of local LAAs is to provide a space for facilitating the dialogue and exchange of knowledge and experience
- Here, we are not representing our institution point of view: we are a group of people with different background and experience that are interested in identifying suitable solutions to our common problems
- *Next steps*

[Explain how often you will be meeting, and which are the next planned activities]

ROUNDTABLE

Topic 1 (T1): 'Tour de table'	Short presentation of all participants, including main expectations for LENSES	(5-10 min)
T2: Setting objectives	What can LENSES do for me? What can I do for LENSES?	(15 min)
T3: Stakeholder mapping	Mapping key stakeholders (Who do you miss in this room?).	(15 min)
T4: Mapping relationships	How do stakeholders relate among them?	(15 min)

TOPIC 1 (T1).- 'TOUR DE TABLE'

5-10 minutes. All

Short presentation of all attendees, institution they represent and main aim for engaging into LENSES.

T2.- REVISITING THE GENERAL OBJECTIVES FOR THE PILOT

15-20 minutes. All

One idea is to hand out two papers to each participants for them to write as bullet points:

- ✓ How do I think LENSES can directly benefit to my organisation?
- ✓ How do I think my organisation can support the development of Pilot activities? (only as data/information providers? or is there anything else that can be done?)

Then, we can collect the answers, read them in loud voice and discuss with all the group. The answers will be later summarised and the overall perception of the group shared with all participants.

T3.- STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

15-20 minutes. All

A preliminary stakeholder mapping will be prepared beforehand, as part of the preparatory work for the organisation of the meeting.

Our suggestion is that you prepare some slides with the following information:

- List of the stakeholders already identified (highlighting in a different colour those participating in the meeting)
- Potential role of each organisation

Then all the participants can help to complete the list and identify roles for other participants, or indeed, extend their own potential role in LENSES.

T4.- GRADING THE KEY CHALLENGES

15- minutes. All

[NOTE: This part could be skipped in case that time is running out or the moderator feels the participants are starting to get tired or losing a good spirit.]

In this exercise, we suggest to prepare a list with the key challenges of the pilot (those previously presented by the Pilot leader) and ask the stakeholders to make a ranked list of their relevance. Participants should be able to add another challenges to the initial list.

Then, we can briefly explain the concepts of water security, ecosystems services security and food security, and ask the stakeholders to rank them in terms of how important is to address these elements within the pilot.

Ideally, we should use a participatory-support tool (i.e. Slido, Mentimeter) in order to ensure that all answers remain anonymous. This should allow to get more trustable information from all stakeholders.

The activity is closed with a short discussion.

Annex 3

LENSES welcome presentation to stakeholders

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LENSES

Learning and action alliances for Nexus environments in an uncertain future

LENSES: PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES FOR SUSTAINABLE WATER, FOOD AND ENVIRONMENT

This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union.
GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]

WHAT IS THE Water-Ecosystems-Food NEXUS?

Freshwater, land, energy and food are essential for human well-being and sustainable development, but these are limited resources and projections suggest that **their demand will be on the rise.**

The Water-Ecosystems-Food Nexus is a useful concept for addressing the **interrelationships of our global resource systems** and to move towards a better coordination and utilisation of natural resources in different sectors, also considering existing trade-offs.

INTRODUCING THE LENSES PROJECT

LENSES is an Innovation Action funded by the European Union's under the **PRIMA programme**, developed by a consortium of 13 partners from 6 different Mediterranean countries and coordinated by the CREA (IT), a public research council.

The project puts Nexus on the map in **very practical ways** (yet founded in robust science) with the aim of delivering a significant impact by driving resource efficiency over different scales to **make communities more prosperous & sustainable while placing ecosystem protection at the forefront.**

Promoting a resilience approach in Nexus management can significantly **increase the capacity of the whole system to adapt quickly to changes and disruptions.**

The LENSES PILOTS (case studies)

- Doñana (Spain)
- Tarquini plain (Italy)
- Pinios (Greece)
- Koiliaris-Crete (Greece)
- Menemem (Turkey)
- Hula Valley (Israel)
- Jordan Valley (Jordan)

The LENSES pilots address different conflicting water and land uses and typical Mediterranean conditions, in terms of e.g. climate conditions and climate change impacts, interaction between surface water and groundwater, potentially conflicting uses of the resources, relevance of agricultural activities, and social context.

What is going to be done in LENSES?

Several methods are going to be tuned up and applied in the pilots in a coordinated way:

HOW CAN YOU PARTICIPATE?

A key aim for LENSES is to **promote participatory approaches** to match bottom-up and top-down priorities in decision and policy-making.

LENSES will conduct **informative meetings, seminars, rounds of interviews, surveys to inform and listen to all stakeholders**, and will organise **3 larger Workshops (1 per year)** where all stakeholders will interact and **build together common desired scenarios** and **pathways** to reach these scenarios.

https://commons.m.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Noun_co-creation_697362.svg

LENSES WILL ALSO ORGANISE KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE ACTIVITIES BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS OPERATING IN DIFFERENT AREAS BUT FACING SIMILAR CHALLENGES

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF ENGAGING WITH LENSES?

- Help us to **avoid that lack of communication and silo-thinking can get a problem** in socio-economic sustainability and environmental conservation of the nexus system
- Get involved in **up-to-date research** and collaborate with some leading research institutions
- **Contribute to increase resilience** to climate change and other potential system disruptions
- Get a more **comprehensive view of challenges and potential solutions** for the natural resource management in your region, including the perspectives of the public administrations, researchers, the private sector, end users and others.
- Learn about the latest **methods and tools for nexus management** as well as on the main drivers and barriers to change

Thank you for your attention!

This presentation reflects only the author's view.
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This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union.
GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]

Annex 4

LENSES 1 pager:

Support material to facilitate initial contacts with local stakeholders (after translation into local language).

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Learning and action alliances for NexuS Environments in an uncertain future

LENSES

Growing competition among different sectors for scarce natural resources presents an increasing challenge to the security of people, nature and the economy, highlighting the necessity of integrated approaches in natural resources management. As a response, over the last decade, significant effort has been put in improving the understanding of the Nexus interactions between Water, Ecosystem, Food (WEF) as a framework to resource security and sustainable development.

LENSES aims to bring this concept to an operational level as a tool for analysis, planning and decision-making for natural resources management, helping to close the gap between science and policy. To address this gap, LENSES will integrate state-of-the-art scientific modeling tools adapted to specific local conditions. With these tools, developed through participatory processes and allowing visualization of evolving WEF Nexus dynamics, LENSES will help stakeholders and policy-makers to design and build clear scenarios and pathways to be translated into actionable policy choices with the aim of ensuring long-run resource security in the face of climate change.

LENSES is funded by the European Union as part of the PRIMA programme, a part of the Horizon 2020 programme with a specific focus on Mediterranean countries. The project is being carried out by a consortium of 13 partners from six Mediterranean countries under the coordination of CREA, an Italian research council. LENSES integrated approach is being tested and validated within seven pilot areas facing different challenges: Doñana region (Spain), Tarquinia plain (Italy), Pinios lower catchment (Greece), Koiliaris region (Greece), Menemem plain (Turkey), Hula valley (Israel) and Jordan valley (Jordan).

Top-down and bottom-up approaches are being combined to tailor the LENSES approach to the specific needs of pilot areas, with stakeholder alliances taking an active role in co-developing, testing and applying the integration of methods. The dialogues between stakeholders will be fed by climate risk assessments, water accounting and footprints, land-use mapping and the assessment of the capacity of Nature-based solutions to address local challenges. The approach will be cemented through the use of Participatory Systems Dynamic Modelling and the development of Participatory Scenarios.

As a result, LENSES aims to elevate the debate beyond narrow sectoral conflicts, to create space and tools for the design and adoption of a longer-term strategic plan for resilience and resource security.

Annex 5

Informed consent form in English and Spanish

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LENSES

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments in an uncertain future

Informed consent form

1.- PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE LENSES PROJECT

What is the research study about? The overall objective of LENSES is to analyze the Water-Ecosystems-Food NEXUS, and develop and validate solutions and tools to facilitate the transition to resilient and more socially, economically and environmentally sustainable systems. These tools include systems dynamics models, natural capital accounting, water accounting, nature-based solutions and participatory scenarios. One of the case study of the LENSES project is **the plain of TARQUINIA, in Italy**.

This document is intended to provide you with information on the LENSES research project, in which you are invited to participate. This project is funded by the European Union (through the PRIMA programme) and is carried out in compliance with EU ethical standards and rules of good practice in research.

Before authorizing your participation in LENSES, you must receive personalized information from the researcher, read this document and ask all the questions you need to understand the details of it.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You may decide not to participate or, if you choose to participate, you may change your mind by revoking your consent to participate at any time without giving any explanation.

2.- WHAT IS MY INVOLVEMENT?

The project, in addition to using specific models and data, will carry out a series of activities to incorporate the knowledge of experts and local knowledge, in order to achieve more useful results. This interview is part of a set of interviews that will provide initial information for the development of the system dynamics model, which will serve to assess the consequences of possible management measures.

The interview will last between 45 and 60 minutes approximately.

In addition, you will be invited to other participatory activities. At the present time, we are considering organizing 2-3 workshops over the next two years to share results and propose a dynamic for the elaboration of visions and scenarios for the future, based on a participatory process.

3.- HOW WILL THE DATA COLLECTED IN THIS INTERVIEW BE PROCESSED?

The processing, communication and transfer of your answers to questions will be carried out in accordance with European and national legislation. At any time, you can access your data (interview notes), oppose, rectify or cancel them, requesting it from the researcher. Only the research team will have access to the data collected by the study. In case the information is transmitted to other countries, it shall be carried out with a level of data protection at least equivalent to that required by Spanish legislation.

The confidentiality of your responses will be maintained:

- The information will be stored in a non-identifiable digital format (that is, a direct relationship between individuals and interview responses cannot be established).
- The research team intends to publish and report the results of the research study in various ways. Whatever the method of publication of the results, it will be done in such a way that you cannot be identified.
- Unless expressly agreed, your name as a participant in the study will not be disclosed, and references in the project's own internal documents will be made as "expert on water, agriculture or the environment", without directly identifying the persons who have collaborated with the research or the organisation they represent.

The interview will be recorded for the sole purpose of gathering relevant information for the development of LENSES activities.

This information will not be passed on to third parties, that is, it will not be shared outside the environment of the partners of the LENSES project who are working on the pilot of the **Tarquinia plain in Italy**.

The person responsible for the custody of the data is Dr. Alessandro Pagano, from the Institute of the Italian National Research Centre (IRSA-CNR).

4.- REVOCATION OF THIS CONSENT

Even if you have consented to participate, you may revoke your consent at any time and request that the data you have provided will not be used in the investigation. To do so, you can write by email to either of these two addresses: mbeamartinez@gmail.com (in spanish), or alessandro.pagano@ba.irsa.cnr.it (in english or in italian). You can also contact us if you have any questions about the project or the use of interviews.

5.- SIGNATURE

I hereby confirm that I have been informed of the conditions of participation in the LENSES project and confirm that I agree to participate.

LENSES LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments in an uncertain future

Consentimiento informado

1.- ACTIVIDADES PARTICIPATIVAS EN EL PROYECTO LENSES

¿De qué trata el estudio de investigación? El objetivo de LENSES es analizar el nexo Agua-Alimentación-Medio Ambiente, y desarrollar y validar soluciones y herramientas que faciliten la transición hacia sistemas resilientes y más sostenibles social, económica y ambientalmente. Estas herramientas incluyen modelos de dinámica de sistemas, contabilidad del capital natural, contabilidad hídrica, soluciones basadas en la naturaleza y escenarios participativos. Uno de los casos de estudio de LENSES se desarrolla en la **región de Doñana**.

El presente documento tiene por objeto proporcionarle información sobre el proyecto de investigación LENSES, en el que se le invita a participar. Este proyecto está financiado por la Unión Europea (mediante el Programa PRIMA) y se lleva a cabo respetando las normas éticas y las reglas de buenas prácticas en investigación fijadas por la UE.

Antes de autorizar su participación en LENSES, usted debe recibir información personalizada del investigador, leer este documento y hacer todas las preguntas que necesite para comprender los detalles del mismo. **La participación en este estudio es totalmente voluntaria**. Puede decidir no participar o, si decide participar, puede cambiar de opinión retirando su consentimiento a participar en cualquier momento sin dar explicaciones.

2.- ¿EN QUÉ CONSISTE MI PARTICIPACIÓN?

El proyecto, además de utilizar modelos y datos concretos, realizará una serie de actividades para incorporar el conocimiento de personas expertas y con conocimiento local, para así alcanzar resultados más útiles. Esta entrevista forma parte de un conjunto de entrevistas que proporcionarán información inicial para la elaboración del modelo de dinámica de sistemas, que servirá para evaluar las consecuencias de posibles medidas de gestión.

La entrevista durará entre 45 y 60 minutos aproximadamente.

Además, se le invitará a otras actividades participativas. En el momento actual, estamos considerando organizar 2-3 talleres a lo largo de los próximos dos años para compartir resultados y proponer una dinámica para la elaboración de visiones y escenarios de futuro basados en un proceso participativo.

3.- ¿CÓMO SE TRATARÁN LOS DATOS RECOPIADOS EN ESTA ENTREVISTA?

El tratamiento, la comunicación y la cesión de sus respuestas a las preguntas se realizará de acuerdo con lo establecido en la legislación europea y nacional. En cualquier momento, usted podrá acceder a sus datos (notas de la entrevista), oponerse, rectificarlos o cancelarlos, solicitándolo al investigador. Sólo el equipo de investigación tendrá acceso a los datos recogidos por el estudio. En caso de que la información se transmita a otros países, se realizará con un nivel de protección de datos equivalente, al menos, al exigido por la normativa de España.

Se mantendrá la confidencialidad de sus respuestas:

- La información se almacenará en un formato digital no identificable (es decir, no se podrá establecer una relación directa entre personas y respuestas a la entrevista).
- El equipo de investigación tiene la intención de publicar e informar de los resultados del estudio de investigación de diversas maneras. Cualquiera que sea el método de publicación de los resultados, se hará de tal manera que usted no pueda ser identificado.
- Salvo consentimiento expreso, no se difundirá su nombre como participante en el estudio, y las referencias que aparezcan en los propios documentos internos del proyecto se harán como “experto en agua, agricultura o medio ambiente”, sin identificar de forma directa ni a las personas que han colaborado con la investigación ni a la organización que representan.

La entrevista será grabada con el solo propósito de poder recopilar la información de interés que sirva para la elaboración del modelo de dinámica de sistemas.

Esta información no será cedida a terceros, es decir, no se compartirá fuera del entorno de los socios del proyecto LENSES que están trabajando en el piloto de la región de Doñana.

La persona responsable de la custodia de los datos es el doctor Alessandro Pagano, del Instituto IRSA del Centro Nacional de Investigación de Italia.

4.- REVOCACIÓN DE ESTE CONSENTIMIENTO

Aunque usted haya consentido en participar, puede retirarse en cualquier momento y pedir que los datos que haya proporcionado no sean utilizados en la investigación. Para hacerlo puede escribir por email a cualquiera de estas dos direcciones: mbeamartinez@gmail.com (en español), o alessandro.pagano@ba.irsa.cnr.it (en inglés o italiano). Puede igualmente ponerse en contacto con nosotros si tiene cualquier pregunta sobre el proyecto o el uso de las entrevistas.

5.- FIRMA

Por la presente firma, confirmo que he sido informado de las condiciones de participación en el proyecto LENSES y confirmo que acepto participar.

Annex 6

Catalogue of methodologies and event formats for dinamisation of workshops

There are a wide range of methodologies that can be used to dynamize workshops and ensure the achievement of objectives in a smooth and interactive manner.

Most of the techniques can be classified according to their function within the workshop and the objectives it pursues (Geissler and Löffter, 2007)¹.

- A) Presentation and activation techniques. These are aimed at introducing the participants among themselves, attracting their attention, breaking the ice and fostering a participative and dynamic environment.
- B) Analysis and data gathering techniques. These are aimed at reflecting about a topic, raise awareness about the importance of a topic, transfer or communication of knowledge and results to participants or gathering data.
- C) Evaluation techniques. These are aimed at evaluating the performance through a selection of indicators that can cover participation, interest, utility, understanding, etc.

The following boxes present a series of examples of techniques within each category.

¹ Geissler and Löffter (2007) Multi-stakeholder management: Tools for Stakeholder Analysis: 10 building blocks for designing participatory systems of cooperation. GTZ, Germany.

A) PRESENTATION AND ACTIVATION TECHNIQUES

SCHOOL BUS

Objective	Make participants aware of the common features (stakeholder group, origin, interests) and interests of the other participants.
Suitability	Big groups with insufficient time for individual introductions and a great variety of profiles and sectors.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of strategic questions (origin, sector, interest, objective) - The organising team members hold labels with the answers distributed throughout the room - Participants need to go the “stop” with the answer that suits them best

WRITTEN NAMES

Objective	Make participants introduce to each other
Suitability	Small groups (<20) where interaction will be important and a networking effect is sought.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Place participants in a circle holding a card with their name - The participants should try to memorize all names within 5 minutes - The cards are gathered, mixed and distributed again randomly - Each participant should find the owner of the name in his assigned card

SPIDER NETWORK

Objective	Make participants introduce to each other and break the ice
Suitability	Small groups (<15) where strong interactions are expected and time available is of 20-30 minutes
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Place participants in a circle. - The first participant receives a thread ball and briefly introduces himself. Holding the thread edge, he/she passes the ball to a random person in the circle, who holds the next bit and repeats the process until all the participants have spoken and are holding a piece of thread, building together a spider network. - The last participant receiving the ball starts an inverse round rolling it back and repeating the information from the participant holding the next stretch of thread.

B) ANALYSIS AND DATA GATHERING TECHNIQUES

BRAINSTORM

Objective	Gather unbiased perceptions/ideas from participants on a topic
Suitability	When there is a need to gather unbiased opinions, perceptions or proposals from the participants
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make small groups with a balanced representation of actors - Write the target question in a board chart and ask participants to think of ideas, write them down on post-its and paste them around the question. - The facilitator should classify them

WORLD CAFÉ

Objective	Carry out good dialogue and exchange of knowledge on a specified topic
Suitability	Any group with space to move chairs.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make small groups of 8 to 10 people to discuss the topic, while seated around individual tables. - The composition of the group can change because everybody moves on to other tables after a short period of time. - One person always remains at the table as the host and, by doing that, ensures that the exchange of knowledge is fast and saved. - The results of all the discussions are presented at the end of the session.

PRO ACTION CAFÉ

Objective	Host conversations about questions and projects that matter to the people that attend.
Suitability	Small groups (<15) where strong interactions are expected and time available is of 20-30 minutes
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opening circle to connect to the purpose of the session - Ask participants to consider a question they would like to explore for the session and if so, they will be called on to share it and invite others to work with them. - Three rounds of conversation (20-30 minutes each) with a specific focusing question to move the conversation through an evolving process. - Feedback in circle: the host of each table shares what was discussed.

FISH BOWLS	
Objective	Facilitate discussion in large groups by having just 3-6 people talk at any one time.
Suitability	Big groups that should have discussions
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who should speak are seated in the centre of the room while the rest of the participants (maximum of 50 people) sit around the outside and observe without interrupting. - You can have “closed” or “open” fishbowls, meaning that the discussion is either exclusive to the selected participants or one or more of the chairs is open to members of the audience who want to ask questions or make comments. -Although largely self-organising once the discussion gets underway, the fishbowl process usually has a facilitator or moderator.

GRAPHIC VISUAL RECORDINGS	
Objective	Make visual representations of the ideas presented by speakers or introducers facilitating understanding to stakeholders
Suitability	Sessions with many presentations and the need to explain multiple concepts and ideas.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Graphic recording artists work hand-in hand with the speakers to visually depict the key points and messages of your session. - These artists can either draw live onstage on a board or they can draw on a tablet/digital device which is shown on a screen.

SAMOA CIRCLE	
Objective	Promote debate within a central group of stakeholders open to contributions from other participants.
Suitability	Debate with a small target group as the centre
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Place target participants in a circle in the centre - Sit in bigger surrounding circle all the participants that can contribute to the discussion - Explain the rules and start the debate with the small group - When someone in the big circle wants to speak they should make a sign previously agreed (e.g. stand up).

C) EVALUATION TECHNIQUES

SATISFACTION FORM

Objective	Evaluate participant satisfaction with the workshop
Suitability	Any group
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare a form with a few closed questions (ideally tick or yes/no) and a space to write suggestions of comments for improvement - Hand it out the last hour before the end or before lunch and pick them up at the exit.

FORM OF PERCEPTION

Objective	Identify or evaluate perception changes in the participants as a result of the workshop-exercise
Suitability	Any group.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hand out a form with a few questions about the topic of discussion at the beginning of the day to record the pre-workshop perception. - Give each participant a number and ask them to write in the form and remember it until the end. - Hand out the same form again at the end of the day asking to answer the questions again and write down their assigned number. - Pair the forms by number and check any changes in perception.

EVALUATION EMAIL

Objective	Check the perception of participants through an online survey
Suitability	Useful when statistical analyses of the answers are needed
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design an evaluation survey and introduce it in an online survey platform - Send the survey by email to the participants to ask for their evaluation of the workshop. - Make sure to keep the survey brief and no longer than 10 minutes.

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